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Survey on AI-PROGNOSIS toolkit for Parkinson's disease care

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Pages

Start Part 1: General Information Part 2: Perceived potential Part 3: Perceptions and attitudes Part 4: Intention to use

Part 5: Additional feedback

Views

Standard

Language

English

Contact

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Part 1: General Information

* Q1: Please indicate your country of residence:

- Belgium
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Other
- Portugal
- Spain
- Sweden
- United Kingdom

* Q2: Please indicate your age:

- 18 - 24
- 25 - 34
- 35 - 44
- 45 - 54
- 55 - 64
- 65 - 74
- 75 and over

* Q3: Please indicate your gender:

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary or gender-diverse
- Rather not say
- Other

* Q4: Please indicate your current employment status:

- Employed full-time
- Employed part-time
- Student
- Unemployed
- Disability allowance
- Retired
- Other

* Q5: Please indicate your education level:

- No formal education
- Primary school
- Secondary/High school
- Higher education: Bachelor's
- Higher education: Master's
- Higher education: PhD or similar

Vocational education
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 168 Hello **Jamie LUCKHAUS** (logout) | Help ▾ | Language ▾

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* Q6: Please indicate your level of digital literacy:

- Basic
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Expert

* Q7: Please select the statement that you relate most to:

- I am related to someone with Parkinson's Disease
- I have been diagnosed with Parkinson's Disease.
- I am a carepartner (e.g. spouse) for someone with Parkinson's Disease.
- I am a healthcare professional working with Parkinson's Disease patients.
- I am at risk of developing Parkinson's Disease
- None of the above

This field is required.

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Pages

Start Part 1: General Information PD Risk Part 2: Perceived potential Part 3: Perceptions and attitudes Part 4: Intention to use

Part 5: Additional feedback

Views
Standard

Language
English

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PD Risk Questions

* Q1: Have you experienced any signs or symptoms associated with early Parkinson's Disease? (select all that apply)

- Tremors or shaking in hands or fingers
- Changes in handwriting (smaller, more cramped)
- Slowed movement (bradykinesia)
- Speech changes (softer or slurred)
- Muscle stiffness or rigidity
- Other
- Balance and coordination problems
- None of the above

Other (please specify):

* Q2: Do you have a family history of Parkinson's Disease?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

* Q3: Have you consulted a healthcare professional about your risk of developing Parkinson's Disease?

- Yes, I have consulted a neurologist
- Yes, I have consulted my primary care physician
- Yes, I have consulted another specialist
- No, I have not consulted a healthcare professional

* Q4: What factors do you believe contribute to your risk of developing Parkinson's Disease? (select all that apply)

- Genetic predisposition
- Exposure to environmental toxins
- Head injuries
- Age
- Other

Other (please specify):

* Q5: Are you currently taking any steps to monitor or manage your risk of developing Parkinson's Disease? (select all that apply)

- Yes, I am using a mobile health app
- Yes, I am using a smartwatch or other wearable technology
- Yes, I am following specific lifestyle recommendations (e.g., diet, exercise)
- Yes, I am undergoing regular medical check-ups

- No, I am not taking any specific steps
 Other (/eusurvey/forms/runner)

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Other (please specify):

* Q6: How concerned are you about your risk of developing Parkinson's Disease?

- Not at all concerned
 Slightly concerned
 Moderately concerned
 Very concerned
 Extremely concerned

* Q7: Would you be interested in using digital tools (e.g., apps, wearable devices) to monitor your risk and manage potential early symptoms of Parkinson's Disease?

- Yes, definitely
 Yes, possibly
 Not sure
 Probably not
 Definitely not

* Q8: What features would you find most useful in a digital tool for monitoring and managing Parkinson's Disease risk? (select all that apply)

- Symptom tracking Direct communication with healthcare providers
 Medication reminders Community support and resources
 Lifestyle recommendations (e.g., diet, exercise) Other
 Progress reports and health insights

Other (please specify):

* Q9: Have you ever used any of the following to assist you in any aspect of your health? (select all that apply)

- Chat GPT
 Google's Gemini
 Microsoft's Bing AI
 Other generative AI chatbots
 None of the above

Other generative AI chatbot (please specify):

Q9a: Please elaborate further on what you are using the tools to assist with (1 or 2 brief comments):

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Start Part 1: General Information Parkinson's Disease Part 2: Perceived potential Part 3: Perceptions and attitudes

Part 4: Intention to use Part 5: Additional feedback

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English

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jamie.luc
(mailto:j

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survey/

Questions about your Parkinson's Disease

* Q1: How many years have passed since your Parkinson's diagnosis?

- Less than 1 year
- 1-3 years
- 4-6 years
- 7-10 years
- More than 10 years

* Q2: Please indicate your self-rated health status:

- Very bad
- Bad
- Fair
- Good
- Very good

* Q3: Which symptoms do you experience most frequently? (select all that apply)

- Tremor
- Slowness of movement (bradykinesia)
- Muscle stiffness (rigidity)
- Balance problems
- Speech difficulties
- Sleep disturbances
- Depression or anxiety
- Cognitive impairment
- Other

* Q4: How do you currently manage your Parkinson's Disease? (select all that apply)

- Medication
- Physical therapy
- Occupational therapy
- Speech therapy
- Exercise and physical activity
- Diet and nutrition changes
- Alternative therapies (e.g., acupuncture, massage)
- Support groups or counselling
- Other

* Q5: Do you currently use a mobile health app to manage your Parkinson's Disease?

- No, I have never used one
- No, I have used one before
- No, I plan to use one
- Yes, currently using one

* Q6: Do you currently use a smartwatch to manage your Parkinson's Disease?

- No, I have never used one

- No, I have used one before
 No, but I plan to use one
 Yes, currently using one

3% Yes, currently using one

* Q7: Do you currently self-track any signs/symptoms related to Parkinson's Disease (using any methods)?

- I do
 I do not, but I intend to
 I do not currently, and I do not intend to
 I have never tracked, and do not intend to

* Q8: Have you ever used any of the following to assist you in any aspect of your health? (select all that apply)

- Chat GPT
 Google's Gemini
 Microsoft's Bing AI
 Other generative AI chatbots
 None of the above

* Q9: What are your primary health goals related to Parkinson's Disease? (select all that apply)

- Learn about my Parkinson's Disease signs/symptoms and patterns
 Learn my expected Parkinson's Disease progression
 Slow Parkinson's Disease progression through lifestyle factors (e.g., diet, physical activity)
 Minimize symptoms with lifestyle factors (e.g., diet, physical activity, sleep habits)
 Minimize Parkinson's Disease symptoms with medication
 Find a more suitable Parkinson's Disease medication regimen
 Be as all-around healthy as possible
 Other

* Q10: What is your biggest challenge in managing your Parkinson's Disease?

- Managing motor symptoms Emotional or psychological impact
 Managing non-motor symptoms Financial burden
 Accessing healthcare services Lack of support or resources
 Adhering to treatment plans Other

* Q11: What features would you find most helpful in an AI-based tool for managing Parkinson's Disease? (select all that apply)

- Early diagnosis and risk assessment Enhancing patient and caregiver engagement
 Monitoring and tracking symptoms Providing educational resources
 Personalized treatment recommendations Other
 Predicting disease progression

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Views

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Part 5: Additional feedback

Carepartner questions

* Q1: How long have you been a caregiver for someone with Parkinson's Disease?

- Less than 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-10 years
- More than 10 years

* Q2: What is your relationship to the person with Parkinson's Disease?

- Spouse/Partner
- Child
- Sibling
- Friend
- Other

* Q3: How would you rate your current level of knowledge about Parkinson's Disease?

- Very low
- Low
- Moderate
- High
- Very high

* Q4: Do you currently use any resources to help you in your caregiving role? (select all that apply)

- Mobile health apps Educational websites
- Online support groups or forums Books or manuals
- In-person support groups Other
- Healthcare professionals None

* Q5: Have you ever used any of the following to assist you in any aspect of your health? (select all that apply)

- Chat GPT
- Google's Gemini
- Microsoft's Bing AI
- Other generative AI chatbots
- None of the above

* Q6: What are the most significant challenges you face as a caregiver for someone with Parkinson's Disease? (select all that apply)

- Managing medication schedules Coordinating with healthcare providers

- Helping with mobility and physical activities Balancing caregiving with other responsibilities
 Managing symptoms (e.g., tremor, rigidity) Financial strain
3% Providing emotional support Other

* Q7: How do you typically track and manage the symptoms and health of the person with Parkinson's Disease you care for? (select all that apply)

- Using a mobile health app Regular consultations with healthcare providers
 Using a smartwatch or other wearable technology Relying on personal observation and memory
 Keeping a written log or diary Other

* Q8: Are you interested in using digital tools to help manage your caregiving responsibilities?

- Yes, definitely
 Yes, possibly
 Not sure
 Probably not
 Definitely not

* Q9: What features would you find most helpful in a digital tool designed to support caregivers of people with Parkinson's Disease? (select all that apply)

- Symptom tracking Communication with healthcare providers
 Medication reminders Community support and forums
 Scheduling and appointment management Emergency alert features
 Educational resources Other

* Q10: How would you rate the overall support you receive as a caregiver for someone with Parkinson's Disease?

- Very poor
 Poor
 Fair
 Good
 Excellent
 Not applicable

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Views

Standard

Language

English

Contact

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- Start
- Part 1: General Information
- Healthcare professional
- Part 2: Perceived potential
- Part 3: Perceptions and attitudes
- Part 4: Intention to use
- Part 5: Additional feedback

Healthcare professional questions

* Q1: How many years have you been working with Parkinson's Disease patients?

- Less than 1 year
- 1-3 years
- 4-6 years
- 7-10 years
- More than 10 years

* Q2: What is your primary professional role?

- Neurologist
- Speech Therapist
- General Practitioner
- Psychologist
- Physiotherapist
- Social Worker
- Occupational Therapist
- Other
- Nurse

* Q3: What settings do you primarily work in? (select all that apply)

- Hospital
- Home care
- Private clinic
- Research institution
- Rehabilitation centre
- Other
- Nursing home

* Q4: Do you currently use any digital tools or apps in the management of Parkinson's Disease patients?

- Yes, regularly
- Yes, occasionally
- No, but I am interested
- No, and I am not interested

* Q5: What are the most significant challenges you face in managing Parkinson's Disease patients? (select all that apply)

- Diagnosing the disease
- Patient adherence to treatment plans
- Managing motor symptoms
- Providing patient and caregiver education
- Managing non-motor symptoms
- Other
- Coordinating care among multiple providers

* Q6: How do you involve (informal) caregivers in the care of Parkinson's Disease patients? (select all that apply)

- Providing education and resources
- Regular communication and updates
- Involving them in treatment planning

- Offering support groups and counselling
- Other

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* Q7: Have you ever used any of the following to assist you in any aspect of your health? (select all that apply)

- Chat GPT
- Google's Gemini
- Microsoft's Bing AI
- Other generative AI chatbots
- None of the above

* Q8: Are you interested in using AI-based tools for assessing and managing Parkinson's Disease?

- Yes, very interested
- Yes, somewhat interested
- Not sure
- Probably not
- Definitely not

* Q9: What features would you find most helpful in an AI-based tool for managing Parkinson's Disease? (select all that apply)

- Early diagnosis and risk assessment
- Monitoring and tracking symptoms
- Personalized treatment recommendations
- Predicting disease progression
- Enhancing patient and carepartner/caregiver engagement
- Other

* Q10: How would you rate the overall effectiveness of current treatment options for Parkinson's Disease?

- Very poor
- Poor
- Fair
- Good
- Excellent

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Part 5: Additional feedback

Views

Standard

Language

English

Contact

jamie.luc
(mailto:j

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Report &
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survey=

Part 1: General Information

* Q1: Please indicate your country of residence:

- Belgium
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Other
- Portugal
- Spain
- Sweden
- United Kingdom

* Q2: Please indicate your age:

- 18 - 24
- 25 - 34
- 35 - 44
- 45 - 54
- 55 - 64
- 65 - 74
- 75 and over

* Q3: Please indicate your gender:

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary or gender-diverse
- Rather not say
- Other

* Q4: Please indicate your current employment status:

- Employed full-time Disability allowance
- Employed part-time Retired
- Student Other
- Unemployed

* Q5: Please indicate your education level:

- No formal education Higher education: Bachelor's
- Primary school Higher education: Master's
- Secondary/High school Higher education: PhD or similar

5%

* Q6: Please indicate your level of digital literacy:

- Basic
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Expert

* Q7: Please select the statement that you relate most to:

- I am related to someone with Parkinson's Disease
- I have been diagnosed with Parkinson's Disease.
- I am a carepartner (e.g. spouse) for someone with Parkinson's Disease.
- I am a healthcare professional working with Parkinson's Disease patients.
- I am at risk of developing Parkinson's Disease
- None of the above

You have indicated that you are "none of the above." At this time, we are only looking for individuals with a connection to PD.

We thank you for your interest!

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Views
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Part 2: Perceived Potential of AI-PROGNOSIS

In this section, we will ask about your thoughts regarding the use of AI-PROGNOSIS mobile apps and smartwatches for self-tracking Parkinson's Disease (PD). Your input will help us to co-design the AI-PROGNOSIS tools.

AI Tools for PD Risk in AI-PROGNOSIS

The AI-PROGNOSIS project utilizes AI tools to assess and manage the risk of developing PD. These tools offer the following capabilities:

- **Data Analysis:** examine a wide range of data, including genetic information, environmental factors, lifestyle habits, and early symptoms, to identify potential risk factors for PD.
- **Personalized Risk Assessment:** provide users with personalized assessments of their risk of developing PD based on their unique data.
- **Early Detection and Intervention:** detect early signs of PD before noticeable symptoms appear, enabling early intervention strategies to potentially reduce or delay the onset of the disease.

Q1: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived potential of the AI tools within AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD risk.

AI-PROGNOSIS tool for PD <u>risk</u> would...	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
*Increase your confidence in the AI tools' ability to accurately monitor and predict PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Enhance your belief that AI tools could effectively manage risk factors for PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Improve your understanding and ability to act on the risk reduction recommendations provided by the AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Strengthen your belief that using AI tools could optimize efforts in managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Raise your awareness of the benefits of using AI tools for monitoring and managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Clarify the potential challenges associated with using AI tools for PD risk management.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Increase your belief that AI tools could address barriers in managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Increase your willingness to use AI tools for monitoring and managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Heighten your motivation to follow the risk management advice provided by AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Enhance your sense of independence in managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q2: Please add any additional comments you have on the use of AI tools for PD risk. (1 or 2 brief comments):

AI Tools for PD Progression in AI-PROGNOSIS

The AI-PROGNOSIS project utilizes AI tools to monitor and predict the progression of PD in patients. These tools offer the following capabilities:

- **Symptom Tracking:** continuously monitor and track both motor and non-motor symptoms of PD using data collected from mobile apps and wearable devices like smartwatches.
- **Progression Prediction:** utilize predictive algorithms to forecast how PD may progress over time, assisting patients and healthcare professionals in understanding the potential evolution of the disease.
- **Personalized Recommendations:** provide tailored recommendations for managing PD progression, including lifestyle changes, exercises, and other interventions aimed at slowing down the advancement of the disease.

Q3: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived potential of the AI tools within AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD progression

AI-PROGNOSIS tool for PD <u>progression</u> would...	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
*Increase your confidence that the AI tools could effectively manage PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Enhance your belief that AI tools could effectively manage PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Improve your ability to understand and act on the progression management recommendations provided by the AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Strengthen your belief that using the AI tools could optimize efforts to manage PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Raise your awareness of the benefits of using AI tools for monitoring and managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Clarify the potential challenges associated with using AI tools for managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Increase your belief that AI tools could address barriers to managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Boost your intention to use AI tools for monitoring and managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Heighten your motivation to follow the progression management advice provided by AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Enhance your competence in managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q4: Please add any additional comments you have on the use of AI tools for PD progression. (1 or 2 brief comments):

AI Tools for PD Medication Response in AI-PROGNOSIS

AI-PROGNOSIS integrates AI tools to optimize medication management for PD patients. These tools include:

- **Medication Monitoring:** continuous tracking of how patients respond to their medications by monitoring symptoms and side effects.
- **Predictive Response:** utilization of AI to predict how patients may respond to various medications and dosages, facilitating personalized treatment plans.
- **Medication Adjustment:** provision of recommendations for adjusting medication schedules and dosages based on real-time data, aiming to enhance treatment effectiveness and minimize side effects.

Q5: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived potential of the AI tools within AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD medication response

AI-PROGNOSIS tool for PD <u>medication response</u> would...	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
*Increase your confidence in using the AI tools to manage medication schedules effectively.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Enhance your belief that the AI tools could accurately monitor and predict medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Improve your ability to understand and act on the medication recommendations provided by the AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Strengthen your belief that using the AI tools could optimize medication regimens.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Raise your awareness of the benefits of using AI tools for managing medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Clarify the potential challenges associated with using AI tools for medication management.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Increase your belief that AI tools could address barriers to effective medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Boost your intention to use AI tools for managing medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Heighten your motivation to follow the medication management advice provided by AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(/eusurvey/forms/runner) AI-PROGNOSIS tool for PD medication response would...		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Language ▾
3%		1	2	3	4	5	
*Support your sense of competence in managing medication response.		<input type="radio"/>					

Q6: Please add any additional comments you have on the use of AI tools for PD medication response. (1 or 2 brief comments):

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Part 5: Additional feedback

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Standard

Language
English

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Part 3: Perceptions and attitudes

In this section, we seek to understand your perceptions and attitudes towards using the AI-PROGNOSIS Modules (i.e., mAI-Health, mAI-Care, mAI-Insights) for managing PD risk, progression, and medication responses. Your input will help us to co-design the AI-PROGNOSIS tools.

AI-PROGNOSIS Modules

- mAI-Health mobile app:** designed for individuals without PD to track their personalized risk of developing the disease. This app uses data from smartphone and smartwatch trackers, along with self-reports on relevant risk factors and symptoms, to provide explainable insights and quantitative PD risk assessments.
- mAI-Care mobile app:** developed for people with PD (PwPD) to monitor disease progression and medication efficacy. This app allows PwPD and their caregivers to access personalized projections of PD progression, track symptoms, and evaluate treatment effects using digital biomarkers, self-reports, and clinical data shared by their physician.
- mAI-Insights clinical platform:** a tool for healthcare professionals (HCPs) to support PD screening, patient follow-up, and medication optimization. This platform enables HCPs to track individuals at risk of PD, monitor patients' status through shared data, view progression predictions, and receive individualized predictions for medication response to optimize treatment plans.

Q7: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived usefulness of AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD.

mAI-Health (risk monitoring) mAI-Care (progression and medication response) mAI-Insights (healthcare professional portal)	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
*The mAI-Health mobile app would be useful for early detection and notification about the risk of developing PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*The mAI-Health mobile app would provide valuable insights for managing risk factors associated with PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*The mAI-Care mobile app would be useful for monitoring the progression of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*The mAI-Care mobile app would offer valuable insights for managing treatment effects in PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*The mAI-Insights clinical platform would be useful for managing medication schedules.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*The mAI-Insights clinical platform would provide valuable recommendations to optimize medication regimens.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q8: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived ease of use of AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD.

mAI-Health (risk monitoring) mAI-Care (progression and medication response) mAI-Insights (healthcare professional portal)	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
*The mAI-Health mobile app would be user-friendly for monitoring the risk of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Learning to operate the mAI-Health mobile app would be straightforward.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(/eusurvey/forms) mAI-Health (risk monitoring) mAI-Care (progression and medication response) mAI-Insights (healthcare professional portal)		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
		1	2	3	4	5
*The mAI-Care mobile app would be user-friendly for monitoring the progression of PD.		<input type="radio"/>				
*Using the mAI-Care mobile app would require minimal effort.		<input type="radio"/>				
*The mAI-Insights clinical platform for healthcare professionalss appears to be user-friendly for managing medication response.		<input type="radio"/>				
*I believe it would be easy to implement the medication recommendations provided by the mAI-Insights clinical platform.		<input type="radio"/>				

Q9: Please rate the following statements regarding your attitude towards using the AI-PROGNOSIS tools in managing PD

mAI-Health (risk monitoring) mAI-Care (progression and medication response) mAI-Insights (healthcare professional portal)	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
*I have a positive attitude towards using the mAI-Health mobile app for managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I believe that the insights provided by the mAI-Health mobile app would be valuable for managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I have a positive attitude towards using the mAI-Care mobile app for managing the progression of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I believe that using the mAI-Care mobile app would be beneficial for monitoring PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I have a positive attitude towards using the mAI-Insights clinical platform for managing medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I believe that using the mAI-Insights clinical platform would be effective for optimizing medication regimens.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q10: Please rate the following statements regarding your intention to use the AI-PROGNOSIS tools in managing PD

	Strongly Disagree 1	Somewhat Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Somewhat Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
*I intend to use the mAI-Health mobile app to monitor the risk of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I plan to utilize the mAI-Health mobile app to manage risk factors for PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I intend to use the mAI-Care mobile app to monitor PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I plan to use the mAI-Care mobile app to manage the progression of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I intend to follow recommendations from the mAI-Insights clinical platform for managing medication schedules.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I plan to adhere to the medication recommendations provided by the mAI-Insights clinical platform.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q11: Please add any additional thoughts you have on the AI-PROGNOSIS Modules (1 or 2 brief comments):

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Part 4: Intention to use AI-PROGNOSIS system

In this section, we aim to understand your overall intention to use the AI-PROGNOSIS tool. Your input will help us to co-design the AI-PROGNOSIS tools

AI-PROGNOSIS system

The AI-PROGNOSIS system employs AI-driven technology, including the previously described mobile apps and smartwatch to gather data on PD symptoms. This data are analysed using predictive AI algorithms to deliver personalized recommendations and prognostic insights, with the aim of enhancing disease management and treatment outcomes.

Q12: Please reflect on the AI-PROGNOSIS system (including AI tools for PD risk, progression, and PD medication response) described earlier, and rate your intention to use it.

Regarding your intention to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system:	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
*I intend to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system to <u>manage PD</u> .	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I plan to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system to monitor and manage the <u>risk</u> of developing PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I intend to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system to <u>track and manage the progression</u> of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I plan to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system to <u>manage medication</u> schedule and follow the recommendations provided.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q13: Please add any additional thoughts you have on the AI-PROGNOSIS system (1 or 2 brief comments):

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Part 5: Additional feedback

Q14: Please provide any additional thoughts or feedback that came up during the survey. All comments are welcome! If you wish to elaborate on any of the questions or add a comment, please do so below!

Please submit your response.

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